

Rice Yellow Mottle Virus (RYMV) Nursery were observed to be B1 resistant. This is because most of the lines developed for RYMV resistance came from adapted upland varieties, such as 63-83, Dourado Precoce, Iguape Cateto, and Moroberekan, which are also B1 resistant.

Cluster analysis of the results by groups of entries from the same origin showed that African and Latin American entries performed at par or better than those from Asia, USA, Europe, and the Middle East with respect to proportion of B1-resistant entries (see figure, b). Of the entries with superior performance, more originated from Africa than from Latin America.

The close similarity in superior performance of improved African and Latin American entries reflects the similarities in the host-pathogen-stress complex. Some traditional varieties have been used more often than others in the parentage of the B1-tolerant lines

Blast scores for 1,253 entries in 1991 INGER-Africa nurseries grouped into major ecosystems or stresses and by region. Scored by *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale 0-9.

originating from different regions (see table). These include varieties 63-83, Colombia 1, Dourado Precoce, Iguape Cateto, and Moroberekan.

The results indicate that adapted genotypes from Africa and Latin America serve as good sources for durable B1 resistance for upland rice in Africa. □

Reaction of some rice cultures to leaf blast (BI), brown spot (BS), and leaf scald (LSc)

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We screened rice cultures Kalinga, CR628-2, CR635-42, Karna, IET7 191, and Intan during the 1988 and 1989 wet seasons in fields with high disease

pressure. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. Plot size was 6 × 3 m. We applied fertilizer 60-75-87.5 kg NPK/ha. Total rainfall during crop growth was 644.8 mm in 1988 and 1,389.3 mm in 1989.

All of the entries were moderately to highly susceptible to leaf BI, moderately susceptible to susceptible to BS, and susceptible to LSc (see table). Days to 50% flowering, plant height, and yield for each culture are reported in the table. □

Reaction of rice cultures to leaf BI, BS, and LSc.

Culture	Disease score ^a			Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Yield (t/ha)
	Leaf blast	Brown spot	Leaf scald			
Kalinga	9	7	7	86	67.8	1.1
CR628-2	9	7	7	97	64.5	1.1
CR635-42	9	6	7	97	77.3	1.1
<i>Checks</i>						
Karna	9	7	7	90	62.1	2.0
IET7191	9	5	7	107	67.6	2.4
Intan	7	6	7	117	67.9	2.0
LSD (0.05)						0.1

^aBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Grain quality

Aromatic and quality rice improvement in Tamil Nadu, India

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Consumers in Tamil Nadu prefer rice Varieties with good cooking quality and scent. These rices receive a premium price in the market and have export potential. Many of them are tall indicas that lodge easily and have low yield potential. We evaluated 10 quality rice varieties of medium duration (around 140 d) during the 1990 thaladi season (Sep-Oct to Jan-Feb) to assess their

performance and feasibility of use as donors for aromatic and quality rice improvement in Tamil Nadu.

We transplanted 30-d-old seedlings in 10-m² plots with 20- × 10-cm spacing. We used 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha.

Milled rice samples were used to assess scent in a cooking test. It was evaluated using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES).